

The Misuse of Antibiotics & Prescription Drugs and How Antibiotic Stewardship Can Help

Kevin Morris^{1,2}, Walencia O. Pereira³, Joe F. Bolanos^{1,2}

1. Research Scientist, SBMT, USA
2. Aklun Biotech, India
3. Graduate Student, Azusa Pacific University, USA

Introduction

- Prescription of drugs is a central component in the treatment process for diseases.
- Since the discovery of the first antibiotic – Penicillin, antibiotics are used extensively against infections.
- Morphine is used widely in pain management.
- Prescription drugs include opioids, sedatives, antibiotics and various other highly regulated formulations that if misused can cause more harm than good.
- The United Nations World Drug Report data from 2023 highlights that non-medical use of prescription drugs and antibiotics is leading to a global cause for concern to public health specially in the post COVID-19 era.
- COVID-19 pandemic is known to cause a range of problems from respiratory to neuropsychiatric issues.
- The Centers for Disease Control Special Report from 2022 focuses how COVID-19 has worsened the fight against antimicrobial resistance (AMR).
- AMR is on the rise due to the rampant and unregulated use of drugs in different aspects of human life, which is leading to the rise of 'Superbugs.'
- There is a potential solution to help fight this next silent pandemic of AMR and superbugs through initiatives such as an antibiotic stewardship program.

Objectives of this study

- I. To search literature regarding the extent of prescription drug and antibiotic misuse or abuse.
- II. To review current guidelines on antimicrobial resistance.
- III. To appraise if antibiotic stewardship programs work and how to implement them globally.
- IV. Discuss limitations and future perspectives.

Method: Literature Search

A focused search and systematic review of literature was conducted.

Databases: PubMed, Scopus, CDC, WHO

Keywords: "antibiotics", "prescription drug", "stewardship program", "COVID-19", "antimicrobial resistance"

Total of 147 studies were identified.

Criteria of inclusion: government sources, peer reviewed publication, legacy literature, year of publication 2010 – 2024.

Criteria of exclusion: only abstract available, personal blogs, literature not in English, year of publication before 2010

Collected data was analyzed for further evaluation and critical appraisal

Antimicrobial Resistance

- ✓ When bacteria, viruses or fungi causing infections become resistant to antimicrobial treatment is when AMR is developed. It does not mean our body is resistant to antibiotics or antifungals.
- ✓ AMR has emerged as one of the most serious threats to public health, responsible for nearly 5 million deaths in 2019 globally.
- ✓ Every year in the USA, at least 2.8 million people are infected with AMR germs out of which at least 35,000 succumb.
- ✓ Antibiotic-resistant infections are estimated to have directly killed nearly 300,000 people in India — including tens of thousands of newborn babies — in 2019 alone, and been a factor in a further one million deaths that year.
- ✓ The illustration (adapted from CDC) below demonstrates how AMR develops (figure 1), jumps from germ to germ via mobile genetic elements (figure 2) and spreads globally (figure 3), creating disruptions.

Figure 1: Mechanisms by which Resistance develops in Microbes

Figure 2: AMR movement from germ to germ. A) Mobile Genetic Elements. B) How Mobile Genetic Elements Work

Figure 3: Global Spread of AMR

Antibiotic Approved or Released	Year released	Resistant Germ Identified	Year identified
Penicillin	1941	Staphylococcus aureus Streptococcus pneumoniae	1942 1967
Vancomycin	1958	Staphylococcus aureus	2002
Amphotericin B	1959	Candida auris	2016
Methicillin	1960	Staphylococcus aureus	1960
Azithromycin	1980	Neisseria gonorrhoeae	2011
Ciprofloxacin	1987	Neisseria gonorrhoeae	2007
Fluconazole	1990 (FDA Approved)	Candida	1988
Ceftazidime-avibactam	2015	KPC producing Klebsiella pneumoniae	2015

Table 1: Some Common Antibiotics released over the years that developed Antibiotic Resistance

Outlook/ Conclusions 12 Point Agenda

1. Need for a massive global public awareness campaign
2. Improvement of hygiene and prevent the spread of infection
3. Improve global surveillance of drug resistance in humans and animals
4. Promote new, rapid diagnostics to reduce unnecessary use of antibiotics
5. Promote the development and use of vaccines
6. Establish a Global Innovation Fund for early-stage and non-commercial research
7. Better incentives to promote investment for new drugs and improving existing ones
8. Build a global coalition for real action – via the G20 and working groups such as the Neuroscience20 (N20)
9. Urgent Need to follow the current guidelines on antibiotic/antiviral/ antifungal prescription
10. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need to stop the spread of germs before they can cause an infection
11. Treatment after the infection occurs is not the only solution and should not be the only option.
12. Need to develop novel decolonizing agents and nanomedicines to stop the spread of antimicrobial-resistant germs by people who may not know they are carriers

Antibiotic Stewardship Program

- ❖ An Antibiotic Stewardship Program can be described as an effort to measure and improve how antibiotics are prescribed by clinicians and used by patients.
- ❖ Improving antibiotic prescribing and use is critical to effectively treat infections, protect patients from harm caused by unnecessary antibiotic use, and combat antibiotic/antimicrobial resistance.

Figure 4: Diagram showing Core Elements of Antibiotic Stewardship Program

Figure 5: Diagram showing Inpatient and Outpatient Interventions for an Antibiotic Stewardship Program. (Used with permission from KDHE-UKHS)

Bibliography

1. Standard Treatment Guidelines for the Management of Substance Use Disorders and Behavioural Addictions. Murthy P, Dhawan A, et al, New Delhi: Tobacco Control & Drug De-Addiction Programme Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, 2020.
2. UNODC, World Drug Report 2023 (United Nations publication, 2023).
3. Yamamoto, V., Bolanos, J. F., ... Kateb, B. (2020). COVID-19: Review of a 21st Century Pandemic from Etiology to Neuro-psychiatric Implications. Journal of Alzheimer's Disease, 77(2), 459–504. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-200831>
4. CDC. (2022, August 11). COVID-19 & Antibiotic Resistance. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/drugresistance/covid19.html>
5. CDC. (2022, October 5). What Exactly is Antibiotic Resistance? Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/drugresistance/about.html>
6. Nogrady, B. (2023). The fight against antimicrobial resistance. Nature, 624(7991), S30–S32. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-03912-8>
7. Varahachalam, S. P., Lahooti, B., Chamaneh, M., Bagchi, S., Chhibber, T., Morris, K., Bolanos, J. F., Kim, N.-Y., & Kaushik, A. (2021). Nanomedicine for the SARS-CoV-2: State-of-the-Art and Future Prospects. International Journal of Nanomedicine, Volume 16, 539–560. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S283686>
8. Morris, K., Nami, M., Bolanos, J. F., Lobo, ... Kateb, B. (2021). Neuroscience20 (BRAIN20, SPINE20, and MENTAL20) Health Initiative: A Global Consortium Addressing the Human and Economic Burden of Brain, Spine, and Mental Disorders Through Neurotech Innovations and Policies. Journal of Alzheimer's Disease, 83(4), 1563–1601. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-215190>